

Debating Modernity And Nationalism: Cross-Cultural Explorations From East And West

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Abstract

Cross-cultural explorations, within diversified perspectival origin of nationalism, is important, to apprehend to be acquainted with it's inner as well as outward dynamics. There are assortments of scholarly writings available and, being produced within aphorism of nationalism's antiquity and, modernity. This paper is an attempt to find out the evanescent characters of nationalism and, grip over the continuity in theoretical perspectives developed over the time in the East as well as in the West. Incontrovertibly, whereon it is arguable, this paper presents a scheme that emotivist part of nationalism transliterates the belongingness and relationships of the ancient view of an organic society whereas, rationalist portion of nationalism undertakes, the requirements of an atomistic society and, mechanistic state. Paper, argues that the concept of Vita-Activa proposed by Hannah Arendt and concept of nonviolent Satyagraha practiced by Gandhi do offer an idea of nationalism that is humanitarian in face and is essential in the age of globalization.

Introduction

Responding to a question, asked in an interview, once John Breuilly stated that, 'I think we need more history and we also need to take on board the new directions in which nationalism studies are going, for example normative studies (e.g. on multiculturalism, on liberal nationalism), policy-oriented studies (again, multiculturalism, also ethnic conflict resolution, constitutional designs) and transnational concerns (e.g. diasporas but also much more mobile patterns of migration which do not create permanent communities abroad). In addition, I would want to stress that despite my criticisms of too much focus on "texts" without "contexts," I would also like to see much more work on subjects like music and nationalism, literature and nationalism, the visual arts and nationalism. I think we will be publishing more in these areas, but work which contextualises such subjects and which is clear about just what aspect of nationalism is involved. There is much to be done.'¹

Going with the concerns expressed by Breuilly and envisioning beyond the framework, needs cross-cultural explorations, within diversified perspectives of origin and development of nationalism, to apprehend its inner as well as outward dynamics. There are assortments of scholarly writings available and, being produced within aphorism of nationalism's antiquity and, modernity. This paper, is an attempt to find out the evanescently characters of nationalism and, grip over the continuity in theoretical perspectives developed over the time in the East as well as in the West. Incontrovertibly, whereon it is arguable, this paper presents a scheme that emotivist part of nationalism transliterates the belongingness and relationships of the ancient view of an organic society whereas, rationalist portion of nationalism undertakes, the requirements of an atomistic society and, mechanistic state.

To begin with, emblematically, we would like to start with the statements of Noam Chomsky, Once he was asked what he would say about people like Gandhi or Martin Luther King, who have done remarkable work to change the world. In response to this question, Chomsky said in a mixed tone that the people who were with Gandhi made him important, seen with all popular movements (Schoeffel and John 2003, 189). It is necessary to consider whether those who were with Gandhi were the same ideologically or politically before joining Gandhi. Gandhi, who discovered nonviolence and Satyagraha as a practical conflict resolution approach with self-purification in South Africa, was no longer the same Gandhi registered with the University College of London in 1888 to study law from India. The self-awakened Gandhi tried to connect the scattered voices of victimized people worldwide and did not base any racial or castes spearhead's interests on this. Instead, he did subscribe to the interests of humanity suffering from class-ridden mechanistic rationality of modernity.

Self-awakening for Gandhi himself is a later event in which he understood modern civilization's violence at the very outset. This understanding of Gandhi distinguished him from the person of law practitioner into the pioneer of spiritualizing politics and involved him in the awakening of humanity against falsely acclaimed redemptions of modernity. His participation in the Indian national movement was the symbolic field for the liberation movement of all, whatever they are exploited of modernity or exploiter in modernity. Gandhi's transformation distinguished him as the world's most prominent power against all types of violence at that time and for forever. Gandhi made politics what Hannah Arendt puts meaning in it by *vita activa* or *action*ⁱⁱ. The outline of politics that would extricate from *Advaita*ⁱⁱⁱ *Vedānta*^{iv} is the action of *Niṣkāma-karma yogi*^v, depicted in *Srimad Bhagavad Gita*.^{vi} *Niṣkāma-karma yogi*: one who did not coddle himself into the material gains only as modernity has produced in the form of a consumerist lifestyle. Modernity in the form of a consumerist lifestyle has caged humanity, in the civilization based on what Hannah Arendt calls *labour*^{vii} and *work*^{viii}. Involvement in material aspects is essential for any creature's livelihood, and in this sense, *labour* is essential for metabolic requirements.

Similarly, *work* is fundamental for familial necessities, but to be strutted on the sphere of *labour* and *work* did not acknowledge humans either in the form of plural existence or a superior creature in nature who can take care of entire humanity. It is *vita activa* or *action*^{ix} that renders homo- sapiens above all for selfless offerings of her services for collective interest and not for material gains to fulfil own metabolic requirements or familial necessities. *Srimad Bhagavad Gita* argues on same direction.

*tyaktvā karma-phalāsaṅgam nitya-tripto nirāshrayaḥ
karmaṇyabhipravṛitto 'pi naiva kiñchit karoti saḥ, 4.20*

[Having abandoned attachment to the fruit of action, always content, nowhere seeking refuge, he is not doing anything, although doing actions.]^x

Advaita Vedānta's vision of *Karta* (doer) believes in *tattvamasi*^{xi} and *Soham*^{xii} (that is you, which I am), representing the rationality in which plural existence is honoured like anything. The rationality of modernism is the singular vision's rationality that is based on binary understanding. Gandhi, Hannah Arendt, Emmanuel Levinas, William Blake, and others have dwelled upon its repercussions very insightfully. The modern concept of nationalism depends on binary understanding under which other is suspicious and therefore must not be allowed to accommodate within the framework of geographical impartibility, which is the nation state's core idea. It is interesting to note that the emergence of nationalism in modern Europe took place in such a time where the atomistic concept of society and individual and mechanistic concept of state was gaining momentum. The phenomenal development of nationalism convoluted within the struggle of then European states. Therefore, nationalism, which seeks loyalty in favour of the state, stationed one against another, and hence nationalism was unable to subscribe to humanism as a goal. Nationalism becomes more and more inhuman with the growing impact of modernity, which projected *labour*, *work* framework lifestyle, and ignored *action*.

In the contemporary globalized world, various tendencies of aggressive assimilation across the world are growing and nationalism crinkling under ethnocentrism's growing pressure at the time of cosmopolitanism. If it is the most rational form of development, in that case, it must subscribe to the values of what Hannah Arendt describes *vita-activa* or, Gandhi reflected in the spiritualization of politics and *Srimad Bhagavad Gita* be fluent in *Niṣkāma-karma yoga*. Focusing merely upon economic and technological development will sure cause the withering away of Homo sapiens from the earth in the form of the emergence of Robo- sapiens what Yuval Noah Harari and others warn about. Therefore, nationalism based on *tattvamasi* and *soham* of *Advaita Vedānta*, Gandhi's, and Arendt's vision of politics is the need of time. We, the people of the present era, having a desire for a better future for human generations, willingly participate in the discourse to positively change the world. Considering upon nationalism as an utmost from of collectiveness, it is most essential to think over the character, which it imposes or demands to every individual in a given society. Does it allow that there will be an oppressive class in society? Does it believe that there will be an extreme system of pollution in due course of development? Does it offer a social dynamics of marginalization or exclusion? Nationalistic answers of these questions will be lethal because nationalism subscribes inclusion, belongingness, and love for the people and nature adjacent. Then the question remains unanswered, why the nations in growing age of nationalism polluted their soil and nature like anything and why did they involved in to the imposition of uniformity of language, culture and religion in very violent way even within that caused relegation of huge numbers of people. It requires another way of understanding upon nationalism that goes back in to the age of organic society in ancient period. In fact, nationalism pitched in the value of belongingness and selfless association among people of the age of organic society in ancient period. However, the interdependency among people of the barter age is not the same as interdependency among people in the industrial age or of mechanistic society of present era. Modern nationalism subscribes belongingness of organic society for the self-centred-egoist human being in a mass- society. The very concept of individual as Macpherson describes in simple market society and possessive market society is not same. Possessive market society operates on Possessive individualism; it means the individual who emphasis on extractive capacity instead of associational capacity to be best fitted in market economy (Macpherson 1962, 51-55).

MacPherson depicted that possessive market society has eight characteristics. For the purpose of present discourse, three of them are essential. First, All individuals seek rationally to maximize their utilities. Second, each individual's capacity to labour is his own property and is alienable. Third, land and resources are owned by individuals and are alienable (Macpherson 1962, 53-54). While, considering on these elements with Hannah Arendt's arguments, appeared in *Human Condition*; it became clearer that possessive market society or what she verbalized modern age is covered around the value of *labour* and *work* instead of *action* and it has not only shortened the respiration of humanity but at the same time it has produced a new meaning of politics inseparable to violence. It was the new manifestation of politics to be skimmed with unreal or unnatural proved by old aged wisdom and legacy in to the real and natural not by consent but on the sources based on violence. Politics in its real root as Hannah Arendt describes, power corresponds to the human ability not just to act but also to act in correct. Power is never the property of an individual; it belongs to a group and remains in existence only so long as the group keeps together (Arendt, *The Human Condition* 1998, 44). Possessive market society, which is the group of self-centred individual, sees politics not in accordance with the group as individuals wants to enjoy their own power and hence they take side to achieve success with whom they consider best for their interest. Therefore, nationalism on the grounds of the conflict posed by aliens or outside identities provides collective identity to the group as a nation but this collective identity washed-out at the time of internal conflicts. People involved in internal conflicts do share certain type of nationalism either in the form of masses or in the form of elites as seen in French revolution and in this framework Hobsbawm is right in saying that nationalism is a class ideology (Hobsbawm 1990, 9-14). In this case, nationalism becomes a tool to establish control over state.

State-centric nationalism is prone to violence because state itself is the highest manifestation of violence as Gandhi has described in the *Modern Review* in 1935. Gandhi wrote that the state symbolizes violence in a concentrated and organized form. A person has a soul, but since the state is a soulless machine, violence can never be redeemed from it; its very existence depends on violence. (Gandhi, *India of my dreams* 1947, 77). In fact, Competitive market economy strengthens enmity among states in early stage of capitalism and to protect the interest of emerging capitalist class nationalism become one of the most powerful elements for collective unity in a given territory. Nationalism in this sense has been used by governing elite to produce certain kind of legitimacy in favour of the elite from masses, what Michael Foucault calls governmentality (Foucault 1991, 87-104). Ernest Gellner has arguably established that, nationalism presumably necessary-inherent in the nature of things, of the Human psyche, of human society. This is the vision nationalism has of itself, of its own status: and, very significantly this status is also often ascribed to it by its enemies. (Gellner 1997, 9). However, he has distinguished early nationalism of Greeks and industrial nationalism after Napoleon (Gellner 1997, 40-42).

Gandhi too has distinguished Indian nationalism as a pre-modern phenomenon^{xiii} joining hands with Vivekananda and critically argued against the view of scholars who believe that British rule and modern means of communications gave birth to nationalism in India. Gandhi holds view that, it is modern means of communications like railways we began to believe in distinctions as we are many nations (Gandhi, *Hind Swaraj and other Writings* 1997, 49). Gandhi comprehends a nation in assimilative capacity in acceptance of plurality. He wrote in hind swaraj that, the country must have a faculty of assimilation. India has ever been such a country. In reality, there are as many religions as there are individuals; but those who are conscious of the spirit of nationality do not interfere with one another's religion. If they do, they are not fit to be considered a nation (Gandhi, *Hind Swaraj and other Writings* 1997, 52). Gandhi distanced himself to arguing in favour of economic nationalism that was in the full swing in Europe at that time, not because it has deciphered in colonialism against which he was belligerent, but he has prudence that it will be destructive for humanity as it has deep-rooted selfishness. Arguing on the same line Leon Trotsky has designated Italian fascism has proclaimed national *sacred egoism* as the sole creative factor of humanity to national history, German fascism proceeded to reduce nation to race and race to blood. Moreover, in those countries, which politically have not, arisen- or rather descended to -fascism, the problem of economy are more and more being force into national framework (Trotsky 1934, 18-19).

Trotsky's arguments has deep comprehensions against economic nationalism and should be inspected further more to draw connections in present discourse. Economic nationalism in its initial phase reduced the gap between nation and state. The idea of economic nationalism suggests that production, exchange, consumption, and accumulation can strengthen the national community and the state power can be and is used for such purpose (Crane 1998, 55). Crane move further and says that economic nationalism is thus something of a misnomer, as most conventional treatments focus on the state, not the nation... state and nation may overlap in various ways but national identity is not simply an expression of state interest (Crane 1998, 55). Assertions of economic nationalism integrates societies on the domestic level that in the form of interest articulation between capitalist class and labour class whose sole advocacy falls under the flagship of state on the name of omnipotent representative of the people in international sphere. But it promotes enmity with other nation as realists have exhibited that state is bound to act within *prisoner's dilemma* to exercise over their interest in an anarchic system

and therefore each and every state attempt to maximize their material gain. In this given circumstances modern nationalism aggregates itself as the quiver to exhaust the possibilities of security within geographical impartiality of the state and, hence nationalism became a golden cage to the people whose future depends on the use and misuse of state centric nationalism by the endeavours of their representatives. What did these representatives of the nation state have done after Second World War is worth to note positively, but it is essential to consider upon three facts in due course of re-examining nationalism to unveil violence in it. That is *age of overkill*, concentration of world's more than two third capital and wealth in the hands of less than one percent people and environmental degradation.

The rationality behind *age of overkill*, concentration of capital and wealth and environmental degradation are the technological rationality. Technological rationality transfigures humans from being for itself into being in itself as Jean- Paul Sartre would say. Modernity, in the name of harmonization or to resolve difference promotes technological rationality instead of critical rationality aiming that it would develop objectivity and that will produce similarity in thought and choices. But, in real sense, objective knowledge of modernity is only an obliviousness of self criticality as a rational being to pledge against other's subjectivity who by its dominance claims specialization over subject concerned. Nationalism, in this regard become a means to favour native system of specialization, bureaucratization and militarization. Kellner Douglas points out in the preface of Herbert Marcuse's *one dimensional man* that, the development of modern industry and technological rationality, however undermined the basis of individual rationality. As capitalism and technology developed, advanced industrial society demanded increasing accommodation of the economic and social apparatus and submission to increasing domination and administration. Hence, a "mechanics of conformity" spread throughout the society. The efficiency and power of administration overwhelmed the individual, who gradually lost the earlier traits of critical rationality (i.e., autonomy, dissent, the power of negation), thus producing a "one dimensional society" and "one dimensional man" (Marcuse 1991, XX). To unveiling modern rationality as the single one reminds Sophist's logic in new appearance. Hannah Arendt, sieve this manipulation and discovers reality behind it. She says the most striking difference between ancient and modern Sophists is that the ancients were satisfied with a passing victory of the argument at the expense of truth, whereas the moderns want a more lasting victory at the expense of reality. In other words, one destroyed the dignity of human thought where as the others destroyed the dignity of human action. (Arendt, *The Origins of Totalitarianism* 1973, 9).

Technological rationality and State-Centric nationalism unites two different aspects of human life, e.g., legal responsibilities and political responsibilities and this conversion creates a space for one dimensional men. Political responsibilities are not obligatory responsibilities because canvassing political responsibilities under legal responsibilities undercuts liberty. Michael Oakeshott used to say that political responsibility is similar to the responsibility breathers in friendship.^{xiv} Nationalism puts on responsibilities over citizens in a friendship manner, but state centric nationalism obeisance over it without legislation. Gandhi thinks differently on whole issue, he holds the view, bureaucratization is the inner plea of centralised production system that suppresses free association among citizens. Thinking over an alternative, he says, granting for the moment that machinery may supply all the needs of humanity, still, it would concentrate production in particular areas, so that you have to go about in a round-about way to regulate distribution, whereas if there is production and distribution both in the respective areas where things are required, it is automatically regulated and there is less chance for fraud...When production and consumption both become localized, the temptation to speed up production indefinitely and at any price disappears. All the endless difficulties and problems that our present-day economic system presents, too, would then come to an end. (Gandhi, *Village Swaraj* 1962, 33).

Growing size of specialised mechanism, which suspects Gandhi in its early phase, in our times has retained itself into the self defining apart with increasing technical tools around us and has changed the visage of nationalism from people's nationalism to bureaucratic nationalism. Mounting complications of life essentially needs bureaucratization, but what it causes on other side too is important to think over. Macintyre, in very firmly argued peace of writing says, The This bureaucratization is itself an important clue to the central characteristics of modern societies and one which may enable us to avoid being deceived by their own internal debates.. Those debates are often stated in terms of a supposed opposition between individualism and collectivism, each appearing in a variety of doctrinal forms. On the one side there appear the self -defined protagonists on individual liberty, on the other the self- defined protagonists of planning and regulation, of the goods which are available through bureaucratic organization. But in fact what is crucial is that on which the contending parties agree, namely that there are only two alternatives modes of social life open to us, one in which the free and arbitrary choices of individuals are sovereign and on in which the bureaucracy is sovereign, precisely so that it may limit the free and arbitrary choices of individual. Given this deep cultural agreement, it is unsurprising that the politics of modern societies oscillate between a freedom which is nothing but a lack of regulation of individual behaviour and forms of collectivist control designed only to limit the anarchy of self-interest... both ways are in long run intolerable. Thus the society in which we live is one in which bureaucracy and individualism are partners as well as antagonist. And it is in the cultural climate of this bureaucratic individualism that the emotivist self is naturally at home (Macintyre 2007, 34-35).

Nationalism in such a cultural climate which refers Macintyre, often used to cultivate national consciousness in favour of centralized capitalist economy claiming most rational form of production based on competitive market system, which not only produces commodity to consume rather it commodify its people and hence they lost faith in themselves as a self reflective and self conscious being. National consciousness within decentralised economy and national consciousness within centralized economy plays two different roles. National consciousness within decentralised economy make available various prospects to its individuals to think and act over *good is prior to right*, but national consciousness within centralised economy make available various prospects to its individuals to think and act over *right is prior to good*. The logic of John Rawl's theory of justice presents its arrangements around *right is prior to good* within the rationale of prespectiveless being. Rawls would be justified in assuming that, it is the perspective which crafts difference among choices of the people that some times lead them to carry a different lifestyle and some times compel them to cart a life differently. Nationalism in this case bridges the gaps between the people who by their free choice and some who within compulsions choose two ways of life, one for prosperity and other for labour and bread. But, Rawl's theory of justice as Michael Sandel has argued, promotes utilitarian values because without perspective choices made by people resembles quantitative differences only. Nationalism in this regards in modern societies offers uniformity, within given sphere of bureaucratic rationality. Michael Sandel's concerns are similar to apprehensions of Gandhi.

Michael Sandel focuses on risk avoidance in terms of national consciousness through centralised economy and says what matters for our purpose is that, in the twentieth century, liberalism made its peace with concentrated power. But it was understood at the start that the terms of this piece required a strong sense of national community, morally and politically to underwrite the extended involvements of a modern industrial order. If a virtuous republic of small-scale, democratic communities was no longer a possibility, a national republic seemed democracies next best hope...But this project failed by the mid or late twentieth century, the national republic had run its course. Except for extraordinary movements, such as war, the nation proved too vast a scale across which to cultivate the shared self-understandings necessary to community in the formative or constitutive sense. And so the gradual shift, in our practices and institutions, from a public philosophy of common purposes to one of fair procedures, from a politics of good to a politics of right, from the national republic to procedural republic (Sandel 1984, 93). Transformation of national republic in to the procedural republic of a country for the politics of right is not a case for America only, in general modernity and centralised economy which has wheels around, transfigured the makeup of politics somehow in all over the world. And it has changed the emotivepublic philosophy of nationalism in to the bureaucraticallycultivated procedural rationality.It was the decline of traditional nationalism from nationalism of self reflective being in to the nationalism of commoditised being. Hannah Arendt scripts it with anti-Semitism and pronounces that, one of these hasty explanations has been the identification of anti-Semitism with rampant nationalism and its xenophobic outbursts. Unfortunately, the fact is that modern anti-Semitism grew in proportion as traditional nationalism declined, and reached its climax at the exact movement when the European system of nation-states and its precarious balance of power crashed (Arendt, *The Origins of Totalitarianism* 1973, 3).

In time of ours anti-Semitism has changed the mask, it exists in bureaucratisation and ethnic fundamentalism. Both have a character to impose mechanical uniformity on its subject. Both have passions for nationalism with singular vision as anti-Semitism has anticipated in the past. This verge of nationalism as Rabindranath Tagore has precisely observed that the rule by the nation is neither British nor anything else, but it is an applied science and is used the same way everywhere. This method is similar to the hydraulic pressure, which is entirely capable due to impersonation. The nature of pressure depends on the shape and size of the machine (in the sense of the nation), but their elemental or abstract form is the same. Many foreign regimes have been established so far in the history of human civilization. All of them have some form of machine. However, the difference between the form of other governance and the form of governance by the nation is that the rest of the rule has been like the handloom and the rule by the nation is like the power loom. Handloom-like rule, maintain association with live sensations and music of life. Whereas, a nation-like rule like power loom continues to make society monogamous (understand in terms of uniformity) and life-less (Tagore 2005, 40). Bureaucraticallysledgehammered nationalism is some how analogous to power-loom type of nationalism, which is not self-critical or self-reflective and is prone to be weighed down. Self-critical and self-reflective nationalism keeps distance to the intricacy of history, as intricacies put forward differences of communities that burst somehow growing harmony among them. Ernest Renan observes, a nation is therefore a great solidarity constituted by the filling of sacrifices made and those that one is steel disposed to make. It presupposes a past but is reiterated in the present by a tangible fact: consent, the clearly expressed desire to continue a common life. A nation's existence is (please excuse metaphor) a daily plebiscite, just as an individual existence is perpetual affirmation of life ... A nation never has a true interest in annexing or holding territory that does not wish to annexed or heal (Renan 2001, 175). Existence of a nation in terms of a daily plebiscite of living togetherness, as Renan has stated not only rests on the glorious memories of past rather it requires forgetfulness, because to be a

national unit people must have to forget their acrimonious memories within which their ancestors have involved like enemies. Renan be fluent in

Yet the essence of a nation is that all individuals have many things in common, and that they have forgotten many things. No French citizen knows whether he is a Burgundian, an Alan, a Taifale, or a Visigoth, yet every French citizen has to have forgotten the massacre of Saint Bartholomew, or the massacre that took place in the South in the thirteenth century.^{xv}

It is astonishing to see the tendencies for the search of ancestor's history in a globalised world; these tendencies would lead the humanity again in ethnic conflicts. Therefore, perpetual plebiscite in living togetherness is essentially required for the peaceful existence of humanity. In Eastern Europe, ethnic resurgence after the disintegration of the Soviet Union has proved ideological and civic nationalism hollow. Likewise, the partition of Pakistan had opened the dilemmas around religious nationalism. However, the unification of Germany indicates the revival of cultural, linguistic, economic, and civic nationalism, contrary to the ethnic tendencies. Not only this, on the one hand, ethnic conflicts in nations around the world are expressing discontent within the space of political nationalism, but on the other hand, nations are becoming more and more dependent on each other to galvanise their economy in the globalised era. Therefore, this is not only an age of extremes instead; this era is the age of contradictions and extremes (Hobsbawm 1994).

Nationalism, becoming again, most powerful element of identity politics in the age of contradictions and extremes to achieve the goals of modernization by the less developed and, to hold the market by the most developed. National consciousness or national makeup, proposes, this paper, is not a modern phenomenon. Psychological traits of nationalism are as old as the human history in reference to identity formation process. Nationalism begins with the need of extensive identity. Need for eclectic identity emerges when various dialects combines to form a language. An all-encompassing perspective of identity needed to the community when various clans combine themselves as a tribe and an inclusive course of identity require for the communities when they prefer exogamy to endogamy. In due course of identity formation, when communities involve in to the broadening their world-view, choose *jus gentium*^{xvi} instead of *jus gentiumprivatum*, *jus gentium* offersequity among native people and equity among nations too and moderates flagrancy based on incredulity. Origin and development of all nation and nationalism is perceptible, somehow from disparity to justness rather than justness to disparity.

Nationalism as an ancient expression may be seen mostly in all of the civilisations existed before invent of Mesopotamian^{xvii}, Alexandrian and Mauryan empires. Emergence of nationalism in ancient societies or even in modern societies, are not similar to each other and unidirectional, though, three different traits may be outlined, which were working behind the scene to formulate each and every nation and nationalism: self-respect as a community, glorification and symbolization of the community as a single unit, fear from unacquainted and desire for assimilation. A vast literature is available to vivid with in proposed direction.

Historian Thucydides has stated in a passage of incomparable brilliance, which democracy had for thoughtful Athenians. A democratic leader, Pericles, in funeral oration for the soldiers who had martyred in Great War of Sparta, exquisitely indicated what we today prefer to say nationalism in terms of self-respect as a community and

I would have you day by day fix your eyes upon the greatness of Athens, until you become filled with the love of her; and when you are impressed by the spectacle glory, reflect that this empire has been acquired by men who knew their duty and had the courage to do it, who in the hour of conflict had the fear of dishonour always present to them, and who, if ever they failed in an enterprise, would not allow their virtues to be lost to their country, but freely gave their lives to her as the fairest offering which they could present at her feast. (Sabine 2018, 12).

Pericles's speech is remarkable in two senses, first, he has symbolized collectivist form of identity which is essential for nationalism and, second he has not focused on enmities that caused war between Athens and Sparta. A similar view of collectivist identity would be seen in *vāk devī sūktam* of *Rigveda* that represents the ancient view of nationalism in terms of glorification and symbolization of the community as a single unit.

*āham rāṣṭrī sa'gamānī vasūnām cikītuī prathamā yajñīyānām|
tām mā devā vyādadhū puruṣtrā bhūriṣṭhātrām bhūryāveśayāntīm|.*^{xviii}

These references reveals the nature of ancient nationalism in its humanitarian face, believing in within organic society, less prone to antagonism. But it is not the case that occurs each and every time. Alexander the great too was a person belongs to the organic society and he is who validated violence and enmity to establish an empire on the name of glorification of Macedonia. In his famous speech before Hydaspes war narrated nationalistic spirit into his troops show's fear from unacquainted and desire for assimilation.

I observed, Gentlemen, that when I would lead you on a new venture you no longer follow me with your old spirit. I have asked you to meet me that we may come to a decision together: Are we, upon my advice, to go forward, or, upon yours, to turn back? If you have any complaint to make about the results of your efforts hitherto, or about my self as your commander, there is no more to say. But let me remind you: through your courage and endurance you have gain possession of Ionia...with all that

accomplished, why do you hesitate to extend the power of meadon- your power- to the Hyphasis and the tribe on the other side, are you afraid that a few natives who may still be left will of her opposition? Come, Come! These natives either surrender without a blow or are caught on the run- or leave their country undefended for your taking^{xix}.

Hobswam, while defining nationalism holds view that the 'nation' so considered, was the body of citizens whose collective sovereignty constituted them as a state, which was their political expression. For, whatever else a nation was, the element of citizens and mass participation or choice was never absent from it (Hobswam 1990, 19). Here, Hobswam's considerations that, mass participation or choice was never absent in nation, is essential to be think over critically, because what makes sharp difference between ancient form of nationalism and its modern version is, sovereignty. Nationalism without sovereignty is the participation in commonly accepted endeavours as a single unit of existence with free will of the people. In ancient societies, the concept of sovereignty, in terms of people's power, as Hannah Arendt reminds was not there in existence. Therefore, the remarks of Hobswam, is applicable to only on modern nationalism, where he says that, in short, for the purpose of analysis nationalism comes before nation. Nations do not make states and Nationalisms but the other way round (Hobswam 1990, 10).

Thinking over, nation; nationalism; and sovereignty, in due course of the formation of nation and nationalism, it is crucial to note that every nation in the past have its phenomenal development in the age of anarchy, in terms of modern day's international relations. But, at the same time, it is required to think over the deferent models of anarchy. For this purpose writings of Wendt's appear, with reflective understanding, he argues that there are three models of anarchy: enmity model of anarchy (Hobbesian model), rivalry model of anarchy (Lockean model), and friendship model of anarchy (Kantian model).^{xx} Nationalism evolves within perspectival difference around it. Rivalry model of anarchy and friendship model of anarchy is the internal aspects of nationalism whereas; enmity model of anarchy is the external perspective of nationalism. But, each and every society, in due course of its lifespan, to find the middle ground, goes through some kinds of enmity within native contrivances and, indorses friendship for outsiders. In relation to the history of organic life on earth, writes a modern biologist, the paltry fifty millennia of Homo sapiens constitute something like two seconds at the close of a twenty-four-hour day. On this scale, the history of civilized mankind would fill one fifth of the last second of the last hour. The present, which, as a model of Messianic time, comprises the entire history of mankind in an enormous abridgment, coincides exactly with the stature which the history of mankind has in the universe (Benjamin 1969, 263).

To unveil, the nature of nationalism, its relationship with 'Homogeneous empty time' and, relationship with Messianic time is significantly required, on the whole with an alternative view of identity formation. For this purpose we would like to consider 'homogeneous empty time', certainly in different way. In Europe, before Christianity, polytheism was in live practice. Polytheism keeps diversified view to fellow countrymen and is, able to accept others more openly than Monotheisms. Therefore, nationalism, in pre Messianic time offers homogeneity in heterogeneous societies based on mutual trust. Nationalism, in contrast, to Homogeneous empty time, within and, after Messianic time, holds not only uniformity of faith, rather than it clutches pessimism against those, who claims alternative system of faith. Although, uniformity of faith, was not devised by the Christianity as a religion itself, instead of concocted by the political power, which then was losing its embrace on what Hannah Arendt calls *action*. And, hence modern nationalism, after Holy Roman Empire, traumatized in to the hands of political actors.

Historicism contents itself with establishing a causal connection between various moments in history. But no fact that is a cause is for that very reason historical. It became historical posthumously, as it were, through events that may be separated from it by thousands of years. A historian who takes this as his point of departure stops telling the sequence of events like the beads of a rosary. Instead, he grasps the constellation which his own era has formed with a definite earlier one. Thus he establishes a conception of the present as the "time of the now" which is shot through with chips of Messianic time. (Benjamin 1969, 263). History is the subject of a structure whose site is not homogeneous, empty rime, but time filled by, the presence of the now. Thus, to Robespierre ancient Rome was a past charged with the time of the now which he blasted out of the continuum of history. The French Revolution viewed itself as Rome incarnate. It evoked ancient Rome the way fashion evokes costumes of the past. Fashion has a flair for the topical, no matter where it stirs in the thickets of long ago; it is a tiger's leap into the past. This jump, however, takes place in an arena where the ruling class gives the commands (Benjamin 1969, 260-261).

After Renaissance, Europe has completely departed with the ancient meaning of progress and adopted Protestant vision of progress, crafted in worldly success and, material achievements. This remarkable change of world view of Europe is, now is the most accepted world view from West to East and, from North to South. But, it has reduced the importance of *public*, whose, intrinsic beliefs, was ever, projected in nationalism. The new definition of progress, transformed *private* in to the *public*, and, hence *labour* and *work*, oriented mind-set dominated the public sphere of collectiveness, pride and honour. Social Democratic theories, and even more its practice, have been formed by a conception of progress which did not adhere to reality but made dogmatic

claims. Progress as pictured in the minds of Social Democrats was, first of all, the progress of mankind itself (and not just advances in men's ability and knowledge). Secondly, it was something boundless, in keeping with the infinite perfectibility of mankind. Thirdly, progress was regarded as irresistible, something that automatically pursued a straight or spiral course. Each of these predicates is controversial and opens (Benjamin 1969, 63-64). Hannah Arendt, in her classic piece of writing asserted about the decline of *public*,

But whatever the future may bring, the process of world alienation, started by expropriation and characterized by an ever-increasing progress in wealth, can only assume even more radical proportions if it is permitted to follow its own inherent law. For men cannot become citizens of the world as they are citizens of their countries, and social men cannot own collectively as family and household men own their private property. The rise of society brought above the simultaneous decline of the public as well as the private realm. But the eclipse of a common public world, so crucial to the formation of the lonely mass man and so dangerous in the formation of the world less mentality of modern ideological mass movements, began with the much more tangible loss of privately owned share in the world (Arendt, The Human Condition 1998, 257).

Nationalism, in present era, hence, converted as an ideology of sophisticated consumers, who are inclined to consume their future in the name of development and, progress. To establish monopoly over resources, sophisticated consumers, developed sovereignty -badgered nationalism. Therefore, a unique tendency can be seen in India and rest of the world that ethnic revivalist are not only penetrating over their ancestral past, rather than they are trying to research their history, to prove that the modern technology, were known to their ancient heroes. Anderson, in his milestone argumentation in favour of nationalism as imagined community, discovered the role of print capitalism, he rightly stresses that,

An idea of simultaneity is wholly alien to our own. It views time as something close to what Benjamin calls Messianic time, a simultaneity of past and future in an instantaneous present. In such a view of things, the word 'meanwhile' cannot be of real significance. Our own conception of simultaneity has been a long time in the making, and its emergence is certainly connected, in ways that have yet to be well studied, with the development of the secular sciences. But it is a conception of such fundamental importance that, without taking it fully into account, we will find it difficult to probe the obscure genesis of nationalism. What has come to take the place of the mediaeval conception of simultaneity-along-time is, to borrow again from Benjamin, an idea of 'homogeneous, empty time,' in which simultaneity is, as it were, transverse, cross-time, marked not by prefiguring and fulfilment, but by temporal coincidence, and measured by clock and calendar. Why this transformation should be so important for the birth of the imagined community of the nation can best be seen if we consider the Europe in the eighteenth century: the novel and the newspaper. For these forms provided the technical means for 're-presenting' the kind of imagined community that is the nation. (Anderson 2006, 24-25).

Now, in the age of e-capitalism, when ethnic revivalist are penetrating over history, in search for technological achievements of their ancestors, imagined community of the nation, would blend them in to the narrowness. And, it would prove to be a more violence prone world, because, technological aspects of life as well as in history, did not promote *public* aspects of human being, instead it glorifies the capacity of violence on each other. We, the people of this generation and, the generations which are about to come would not like to be crushed either by nationalism of own or by nationalism of others. Therefore, nonviolent- nationalism is the only way of our survival. For this, as Gandhi used to say, that one must learn the art of killing in the training for violence, so one must learn the art of dying in the training for nonviolence (Douglass 2019, 1-2). To summing up the paper, it would be justified to quote James W. Douglass who in searching of the seeds of life and death of Gandhi has narrated a story took place in India House London, where he was called by Savarkar to address the people on *Dussehra* on October 24, 1909.

Gandhi's talk drew on the Ramayana as a vision of suffering for the truth. The epics main characters, he said, showed the way to freedom through suffering. He spoke of Rama the incarnation of God, suffering in exile, Sita's pure endurance incapacity, and Laxmana's practice of penitential disciplines....Savarkar draw a different lesson from the same story Rama, he proclaimed...(Raja Ram) only after slaying Ravana, the symbol of oppression and injustice. Slaying Ravana was to be taken literally (Douglass 2019, 31).

Glorifying *Rama* as a character of suffering by Gandhi represents a non-violent vision to imagined communities, whereas glorifying *Rama* as a character of masculine, militarists warrior by Savarkar too is a depiction of imagined communities. One focuses on the importance of non-violent civilization and non-violent nationalism whereas latter emphasizes on militarized civilization and nationalism. In the age of overkill, where we are living, non-violent civilization and non-violent nationalism is preferable. Like Gandhi and Hannah Arendt, Mazzini declared that every people had its special mission and that mission constitutes its nationalism. This special mission is only a particular fulfilment of the general mission of the Humanity. Mazzini's concept of nationalism explores the humanitarian character of nationalism that is similar with Gandhi, *Humanity is the association of nationalities, aligns of the peoples in order to work out their mission in peace and love; the organization of free and equal peoples that shall advance without hindrance or impediment (Mazzini 1944, 139-140).*

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